

SPIDER: ML Applied to 5G Network Cyber Range

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Abstract—The 5G mobile network infrastructure is highly related to the latest virtualisation technology, which exposes it to new cyber-attack vectors. Thus, there is a growing need to train cybersecurity experts in the use of appropriate tools to prevent attacks on mobile networks. To meet this need, there are systems called cyber range, among them Spider is specially oriented to train experts in cybersecurity with mobile networks such as 5G. In this paper we are going to indicate how to integrate a module with ML tools in Spider cyber range, how it works and how it can be used to train new experts.

Keywords—5G, machine learning, range, security.

I. INTRODUCTION

There is a demand for using Machine Learning (ML) in network automation for 5G networks management aligned with the latest developments in the field of virtualisation and the adoption of cloud-based architectures for 5G. One promising solution is using ML-based analysis techniques to provide security, with the emergence of new points of vulnerability and exposure to new attack vectors. 3GPP introduced in Release 15 (R15), the Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) to deliver data analytics, opening the path towards ML automation. Consequently, Security Monitoring Analytics systems [1] emerge using ML techniques to detect network attacks (e.g. [2] and [3]). Moreover, malicious agents are moving forward in the same directions to use ML for their activities or to deceived ML inference engines [4]. As a consequence, exists an increasing demand for ML operation expert personnel. There are systems called cyber-ranges that are oriented to support and train cyber-security personnel (some examples of cyber range systems [5] and [6]). These cyber training arenas should be enhanced with ML-based tools to address incoming threats in 5G networks.

Spider [7] is a Cyber Range platform, designed to train cybersecurity experts in telecommunications environments, among others, it is oriented to cover all the cybersecurity needs of the 5G network environment. Spider platform is not only aimed at training ethical hackers or experts, but also aims to improve their level as well as train risk assessors and non-expert users. Then, a typical training process in Spider cyber range has one or two teams: (1) The red team who aims to attack or detect vulnerabilities of a system. This team is composed by teachers and experts. (2) The blue team who aims to protect or detect attacks in a system. This team is composed by trainees.

In this paper we are going to describe how a module with machine learning tools can be integrated into the Spider cyber range, how it works and how it can be used for training.

II. SYSTEM INTEGRATION

Spider cyber range platform is complex and is capable of injecting realistic traffic on a 5G network infrastructure. The ML module is connected to the Spider 5G Network as a virtual machine which receives injected traffic to detect attacks (this connection is shown in the Figure 1). Then, the ML module (Defensive Toolbox) is integrated into the Spider platform architecture with the Machine Learning Orchestrator module which chooses the specific ML model to be deployed inside the virtual machine (the integration is shown in Figure 2).

Fig. 1: Capture and classification process with a ML module

In the following subsections we will detail how the realistic traffic which the Spider platform can inject is generated and how the ML module detects attacker connections from it.

A. Traffic Generation

Spider Cyber Range platform is able to inject a controlled and realistic traffic that was designed in the Mouseworld laboratories of Telefonica RD adapted to 5G mobile networks (for more information about Mouseworld see [8]). This traffic generation system allows deploying complex network scenarios, running servers and clients that follow realistic interaction patterns with both internal and external services (e.g. web, video, cloud, cyber-attacks, ...). The traffic generated in this way is taggable, which subsequently allows machine learning models to be trained and their performance to be verified in realistic scenarios (for more information see [2]). Additionally, the generated traffic can be captured in binary PCAP files by a software called tcpdump to train new ML models or re-inject it for further testings.

B. Machine Learning Module

The ML module is a virtual machine that receives the copy of all traffic injected in Spider 5G network through a mirror interface. The traffic arriving at this module is captured by software called tstat [9]). Then, tstat extracts network statistics summarising the state each connection per captured packet

Afterwards, data preprocessing and machine learning model classification are performed by means of a script (coded

Fig. 2: ML module integration into Spider Cyber Range

in Python in this case) which was selected by Machine Learning Orchestrator. The script extracts from the CSV file the statistics of each connection. The features to be used by the ML model are transformed by applying Standard Scaling according to the mean and standard deviation of the features used to train the corresponding model (for more information about a specific ML model [2]).

Then, the machine learning model is provided with the input features it needs to perform the prediction. The models used in this module are usually supervised classifiers that indicate the confidence level of the classification. The confidence level is measured as a percentage and normally the classifier identifies the connection as an attacker when it has a confidence of more than 50%. The minimum confidence level for accepting a connection as an attacker can be modified.

Finally, the classified connections are reported out of the machine learning module with their identifier and confidence level, to a dashboard integrated in Spider Cyber Range. In the dashboard the results can be reviewed by the user.

III. TRAINEE TRAINING PROCESS

The training process in Spider's Cyber Range with ML tools consists of getting the student used to working with ML-based tools, tuning the models and interpreting the model results in mobile network environments such as 5G. The student can select a generated traffic with different density (more attack traffic or a specific service traffic), can choose the right ML model (e.g. a faster or more accurate one) or can modify the ML model settings (e.g. the minimum confidence level for accepting a connection as an attacker). Then, the trainee will always be able to review and compare the results of various ML models on the Spider Cyber Range dashboard. Specifically, in a Spider scenario the trainee is part of the blue team and has to test various confidence values of a ML model to detect cryptomining attacks.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper it has been shown how the ML module is integrated into Spider cyber range platform, how realistic

network traffic is generated, how the ML module detects attacker connections and how it communicates the results to Spider dashboard. Finally, it is also explained how trainees can learn with this module on Spider cyber range platform.

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